

Br₂ is according to the reaction

This evolution of Br₂ created complexity, which is also an oxidising agent, in the determination of the stoichiometry of the reaction.

The rate law for the reaction is represented as

$$\frac{-d}{dt} \text{Br(V)} = K_4 [\text{Br(V)}] [\text{Glucose}] [\text{H}^+]^2$$

Now for a definite H⁺ concentration, which are reproduced in the system hence act as catalyst, the rate law reduces to

$$\frac{-d}{dt} \text{Br(V)} = K_2 [\text{Br(V)}] [\text{Glucose}]$$

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Effect of Halide Ions on Cathodic Polarization of Nickel in Presence of Dicyandiamide and Related Compounds in Sulphuric Acid

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THE synergistic effect of anions and amines in corrosion inhibition of iron in acid solution has been investigated by a number of workers¹⁻⁴. Also the adsorption of anions on metal surfaces has been investigated by different investigators⁵⁻⁹. However, such investigations on the effects of halides on the corrosion of nickel in acid solution are recent and rare¹⁰⁻¹². The present investigation is concerned with the effect of halides on cathodic polarization of nickel in deaerated 1N sulphuric acid in presence of dicyandiamide, biguanide and guanyl urea.

Experimental

Nickel (99.9% purity) used as electrode, was in the form of beads of circular surface area 0.2 sq. cm. The galvanostatic method used for steady state polarization studies consisted of a constant current generator and one vernier potentiometer having different channels for measuring corrosion current and corrosion potential. All experiments were carried out at 25 ± 1° in inert atmosphere. A saturated calomel electrode was used as reference electrode.

Results and Discussion

The results of the polarization measurements are generally interpreted in terms of Tafel parameters. The E_{corr}, cathodic Tafel slopes, exchange current densities (obtained by extrapolation method) have been tabulated in Table 1. It can be seen that the open circuit corrosion potential is gradually shifted from 232 mv (vs SCE) in pure sulphuric acid to 246 mv, 370 mv and 416 mv with the addition of chloride, bromide and iodide ions respectively. The open circuit corrosion potentials of nickel in sulphuric acid is 232 mv (vs SCE) and the addition of dicyandiamide, guanyl urea and biguanide shifts it to 216 mv, 217 mv and 242 mv. The corresponding changes of Tafel slopes are, however, not so marked in presence of organic compounds. The effect of halides on the exchange current densities is also quite apparent from the Table 1.

In presence of chloride ions, dicyandiamide and guanyl urea shift the open circuit potential to more negative direction but this shift is not so prominent in case of biguanide. Dicyandiamide and guanyl urea shift open circuit potential towards positive direction as compared to the solutions containing

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF HALIDE IONS ON THE CATHODIC POLARIZATION OF NICKEL IN 1N SULPHURIC ACID

Composition of solutions :
 $10^{-3}M$ Inhibitor + $10^{-4}MK^+X^- + 1NH_2SO_4$ (X^- , halide)

Solution	Open circuit corrosion potential - mv \pm 5mv	Equib. exchange current density mA/cm ²	Cathodic Tafel slope b _c mv/dec. \pm 4mv
1N H ₂ SO ₄	232	.0018	115
+ Cl ⁻	246	.0032	125
+ + Dyc	280	.0042	130
+ + Big	244	.0018	115
+ + GU	362	.020	100
+ Br ⁻	370	.012	120
+ + Dyc	415	.020	90
+ + Big	423	.028	110
+ + GU	260	.0022	120
+ I ⁻	416	.010	65/175
+ + Dyc	330	.012	95
+ + Big	265	.0025	115
+ + GU	267	.004	125
+ + Dyc	216	.00075	115
+ + Big	242	.00034	110
+ + GU	217	.00024	105

Dyc : Dicyandiamide, Big : Bignamide, GU : Guanyl Urea.

only chloride or only inhibitor solution. In presence of bromide ions all these compounds shift the potential towards negative directions. It is interesting to note that the open circuit corrosion potentials of all the solutions containing iodide ions are more negative than those of the respective inhibitor solutions but more positive than that of iodide solution.

The Tafel slope and exchange current density for nickel are found to be 115 mv/decade and .0018 mA/cm² respectively. These parameters are in reasonable agreement with those obtained by others for nickel taken in single crystal form and in different acid media^{10,13,14}. The corrosion potential of nickel in the ϕ -scale is +0.06 volts³. Thus it is quite reasonable to assume that at this open circuit corrosion potential the surface charge on nickel is positive and would favour the adsorption of negatively charged ions. And thus, iodide ions, due to their large size and easily deformable electron shell, are most strongly adsorbed. However, the existence of two Tafel slopes in presence of iodide ions is probably due to the change of metal/iodide adsorption from a state of physisorption to chemisorption as proposed by Feller *et al*¹⁵.

Mikhailova *et al*¹⁶ have shown that the adsorption of 'onium' type of compounds in sulphuric acid in presence of halides on nickel increases from chloride, bromide to iodide and the increase in overpotential is up to 65-75 mv in presence of iodide ions. According to Hackerman *et al*⁶ the adsorption of organic materials is not always a direct combination of organic molecules with the metal surface itself but that in some cases adsorption of inhibitors takes place through already adsorbed halide or sulphate ions. Thus, the nitrogen

containing organic compounds used in the present investigation, though, remaining as organic cations in solution, influence the cathodic partial process synergistically. All the organic compounds increase the overpotential in presence of iodide ion and thus supporting the above views.

Thus the synergistic behaviour of the organic compounds, on nickel in 1N sulphuric acid, in presence of halides may be interpreted due to the co-adsorption of the halide ions and the organic cationic compounds, though at higher cathodic potentials role of halide ions adsorption decreases due to their desorption from the electrode surface.

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